

РАЗДЕЛ. ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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**EFFICIENCY OF WAVERING PROCEDURE
FOR MILL PLANT DIAGNOSTICS**

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Annotation: In the practice of testing materials, separate parts, constructions utilized in mechanical engineering, widely adoption got vibration test, often in the wide range frequency. From economical point of view drive and realization of stable frequency and amplitude of judder with some advantage has a manageable electromagnet vibration system. Lately, because of development of semiconductor equipment, there is an opportunity of creating more effective manageable systems in terms of electromagnet vibration exciters.

Keywords: mill plant, wavering, diagnostics, efficiency, electrical power

**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРОЦЕДУРЫ ВИБРАЦИОННОЙ
ДИАГНОСТИКИ МЕЛЬНИЧНЫХ УСТАНОВОК**

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Аннотация: В практике испытаний конструкций мельничных установок, широкое распространение получили вибрационные испытания, часто в широком диапазоне частот. С экономической точки зрения привод и реализация стабильной частоты и амплитуды вибраций с некоторым преимуществом имеет управляемую электромагнитную вибрационную систему. В последнее время в связи с развитием полупроводниковой техники

появилась возможность создания более эффективных управляемых систем на основе электромагнитных вибровозбудителей.

Ключевые слова: мельничные установки, колебание, диагностика, эффективность, электрическая мощность

Any system can oscillate when it is forced to do so externally; the term “vibration” in mechanical engineering is often reserved for systems that can oscillate freely without applied forces. Sometimes these vibrations cause minor or serious performance or safety problems in engineered systems. The role of mechanical vibration analysis should be to use mathematical tools for modeling and predicting potential vibration problems and solutions, which are usually not obvious in preliminary engineering designs. If problems can be predicted, then designs can be modified to mitigate vibration problems before systems are manufactured.

Vibrations can also be intentionally introduced into designs to take advantage of benefits of relative mechanical motion. Unfortunately, knowledge of vibrations in preliminary mechanical designs is rarely considered essential; so many vibration studies are carried out only after systems are manufactured. In these cases, vibration problems must be addressed using passive or active design modifications. Sometimes a design modification may be as simple as a thickness change in a vibrating panel; added thickness tends to push the resonant frequencies of a panel higher leading to less vibration in the operating frequency range.

Design modifications can also be as complicated as inserting electromagnet vibration system. Research on mechanical vibration and methods for its elimination presently gained an importance. Such systems are much simpler in preparing and repeating. But energetic rendering alike systems were not learnt enough. Autonomic electromagnet vibration exciter consisted of electromagnet, non linear intensifier transducer of speed, connected to the entrance of exciter were analyzed in this works. There were taken the solution of frequency and amplitude of vibration, with due regard for non linearity of the system [1-5].

Practical important reading in such systems is efficiency. We shall consider the balance of energy in the systems. Using from the net power.

$$P = \Delta P_{np} + \Delta P_H + \Delta P_{cm} + \Delta P_M + P_b + \Delta P_b + \Delta P_{bcn}, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta P_{np} = \eta \cdot P$ – loss of power in transformers is inventor and rectifiers;

$\gamma_{np} \approx 0,7 \div 0,95$ – efficiency rectifier;

ΔP_M – loss in copper wind ding;

P_b – used power;

ΔP_b – loss the used power;

ΔP_{cm} – loss in steel magnetic conductor vibration exciter;

ΔP_{bcn} – loss in auxiliary equipment – systems of management, protection, signaling and ventilation;

ΔP_H – loss in worked out pressure.

Determination of loses

ΔP_b – is one of the most difficult tasks of vibration equipment.

Their quantity completed depends on conditions vibrations transportation and characteristic of pressure [6-9].

Nowadays there is no practical suitable technique defining them, experimental. Medium value of using power P_b , necessary for supporting settled vibration is:

$$P_b = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T Q \cdot X \cdot \omega \cos \alpha dt \tag{2}$$

where α – angle is between vector power Q and vibration transmission X parties of pressure.

Higher harmonics make dynamic pressure on the construction electromagnet vibration exciter, not permitting considerable extension of productivity. That does why the energy, for exciting higher pal eats can be determined as the losses. Medium value of these losses ΔP_b can be defined from [10-12]. Active used power of system from the net equals:

$$P = UI_1 \cos \nu \tag{3}$$

where U – operating value of tension of net;

I_1 – operating value of the first harmonic of current;

ν – the angle of thyristor inventor turning on.

Efficiency of transformations in the system of regulations of electromagnetic vibration exciter can be showed as followed

$$\eta = \frac{P_b}{P + \Delta P_{np} + \Delta P_M + \Delta P_{cm} + \Delta P_{bcn} + P_b + \Delta P_b} \tag{4}$$

The other a most important energetic readings is coefficient of power S

$$\lambda = \frac{P}{S} \quad (5)$$

Coefficient λ is defined on the entrance of bridge single phase receivers feeding the inverter and winding biasing by famous formulas. In such case:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} \cos \nu \quad (6)$$

The increasing of coefficient of capacity can be include to the entrance of rectifier to the battery of capacitor or use a special scheme of rectifying, for example with zero diode.

Increasing the efficiency can be done by decreasing the power, using on hipless harmonic. In the systems with constant biasing in the amplitude vibration transferring exists usually constant contented, first haring, second and third harmonic.

Working on the first harmonic for weakening of the second harmonic one must increase constant content magnetic stream loused linear height linear height of first and hard harmonic. That's why one should choose the quantity of constant biasing in 1.1-1.3 times more amplitude changeless contented of general stream. The other method of increasing of efficiency is generally accepted.

During working out of new vibration machines calculation of power necessary for supporting the vibration of are difficult task. Such calculation must be leased on the set dissipative resistance but, as a rule there is no accurate notion about them. Even experimental research does not bring clearness them.

That's why serious calculations of power of engines during creating new vibration machines are possible. By above mentioned causes often the only criteria is maximum medium power, which can be realized vibration exciter in such conditions [13-15].

In some cases the maximum medium power practically reached and that are why adoring mentioned criteria is becoming necessary and enough. In linear like system the medium power reaches:

$$P_{b \max} = \frac{F_a^2 \omega}{4(c - m \omega^2)} = \frac{F_a^2 \omega}{4m(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)}, \quad (7)$$

where F_a – amplitude forced power;

ω – frequency of vibration;

c – resiliently of spring system;

m – mass worked part together joined weight of pressure;

ω_0 – own frequency of mechanical sub system.

Dissipative resistances are often linear functions of speed, the king of this functions in very cases are unknowns. And the (7) gives enough accurate for engineering calculations result, if vibration happened with frequency of forced power without stopping ultimate duration.

In theoretical terms, the problem of vibration diagnostics can be considered in relation to the operation of complex systems according to the actual technical state as part of the problem of controlling a random process based on indirect information about the process. At the same time, process control is often carried out in conditions of incompleteness and uncertainty of information.

Indirect information lies in the fact that information that has passed through a dynamic system is used to determine the state. Incompleteness of information is due to technical feasibility, and uncertainty is due to inaccuracy of the problem statement and description of the diagnosed conditions. For a successful solution to the recognition of states, the statistics of correspondences of the vibration image are selected, which is ensured by the correct choice of vibration parameters. The technique of data processing is provided by a special computer program that translates the measured electrical data into a numeric format of velocity and vibration acceleration.

These are subsequently processed into a plot. Interpretation of results is processed as one of the elementary measurements for a particular production machine and the results allow recommendation on production tasks; especially mass production, appropriate and optimal working conditions bring the production with the lowest machine wear and prolong its life and functionality. At the same time, the measurement is one part of the whole complex in which it will be possible to form an appropriate mathematical statistics' intersection of elementary indicators, in the form of a frequency spectrum of signal, which is clearly distributed in amplitude and frequency. The company benefits are less cost, and production benefits are less losses, increased machine life, and higher quality production.

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